

Investigating the distribution of WeChat mentions to scholarly papers in China

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Introduction

With the fast development of altmetrics, science policymakers and researchers are endeavoured to use altmetrics for assessment practice and scholarly communication. Following the structure proposed by Yu, Xu, Xiao and Hemminger (2017), one may be curious to know how altmetrics is applied in specific countries (i.e., the local altmetrics). Previous studies are mainly focused on international platform based altmetrics such as Twitter and Facebook. For countries where these platforms are seldom used or restricted, for example, in China, these types of altmetrics are no longer quite useful.

WeChat has surpassed Weibo to be the largest social media platform in China. It plays an important role in scientific activities (Nature Methods Editorial, 2020), scholarly communication (Cong, Fang, & Costas, 2022; Yu & Li, 2021) and academic evaluation.

This study would, to the best of our knowledge, the first attempt to tap into WeChat altmetrics. Distribution of WeChat mentions to Chinese scholarly articles will be revealed. It complements the study of global altmetrics by presenting an important local altmetrics.

Methodology

CNKI is the largest and most authoritative academic database for Chinese papers. In total, 8,490 Chinese academic journals are indexed. In June 2022, bibliographic data of all 177,959 scholarly papers published in January, 2020 were collected. After that, 40,361 papers that were published in core journals indexed by CSSCI or CSCD were extracted.

WeChat mentions to these scholarly papers were collected with a self-designed program. WeChat had not provided API for data collection, therefore, the program used the API from *weread.qq.com* (a product launched by the same company and shares WeChat data), and retrieved WeChat mentions using title of the scholarly paper, because our pilot study showed that title is the dominant way of WeChat mentions to scholarly papers. In total 21,134 WeChat articles from 4,923 WeChat accounts were harvested. 7,970 scholarly papers were mentioned, so the coverage of WeChat mentions was 19.8%.

For each WeChat article that mentions scholarly paper, the number of readers, likes, comments, real-time readership were also collected.

Result

Immediacy distribution of WeChat mentions

As shown in Figure 1, 56% of WeChat mentions to scholarly papers occurred within 180 days after publication. In specific, 12% of them occurred prior to the formal publication date due to online first and other novel publication patterns. 19% of them occurred within 7 days, and 27% of them occurred within 30 days.

Figure 1. Immediacy distribution of WeChat mentions to scholarly papers

Paper level distribution of WeChat mentions

As shown in Figure 2, paper level distribution of number of WeChat mentions is skewed. In specific, 20% of papers have accumulated 49% of number of unique users and 59% of total number of WeChat mentions. The most frequently mentioned paper has attracted 114 mentions from 94 unique WeChat users.

Figure 2. Paper level distribution of number of WeChat mentions (NUU versus NP)

Journal level distribution of WeChat mentions

As shown in Figure 3, journal level distribution of WeChat mentions conforms to Bradford law. The core area consists of 10 journals. The most mentioned journal is *Food Science* which alone has attracted 3.4% of total number of WeChat mentions. It is followed by *Ecology and environmental science* and *Physics*, with 1.4% and 1.0% respectively.

Figure 3. Journal level distribution of number of WeChat mentions

Account level distribution of WeChat mentions

In total, 4,923 WeChat accounts have posted articles that mention scholarly papers in the dataset. As shown in Figure 4, 66% of WeChat accounts have posted only 1 article that mentions scholarly paper. 88% of them have mentioned less than 5 papers. In general, institutional accounts have posted more WeChat articles than individual accounts.

Figure 4. Account level distribution of number of WeChat mentions

Subject level distribution of WeChat mentions

As shown in Figure 5, subject level distribution of WeChat mentions is fairly even. The most highly mentioned subject is *Philosophy and Humanities* (percentage = 22%). It is followed by *Social Science I* (percentage = 12%) and *Engineering Science and Technology I* (percentage = 12%).

Figure 5. Subject level distribution of number of WeChat mentions.

Conclusions

Main conclusions are drawn as follows. (1) The coverage of WeChat mentions to Chinese core journal papers is 19.8%. It is relatively high considering the low coverage of most altmetrics sources. (2) The immediacy of WeChat mentions as measured by 180 days of time window is 56%. This is equivalent to news mentions (56%), lower than Facebook mentions (74%), Weibo mentions (69%) and Twitter mentions (64%), but higher than policy document mentions (12%). (3) The skewness of number of WeChat mentions is quite close to that of citations. 20% of papers have accumulated 59% of WeChat mentions, in comparison, it is 61% for citations, 48% for Facebook mentions, 74% for news mentions, 72% for Weibo mentions and 76% for Twitter mentions. (4) Journal level distribution of WeChat mentions conforms to Bradford law. 10 core journals can be identified. (5) Most WeChat accounts (88%) have posted few (less than 5) articles that mention scholarly paper. (6) *Philosophy and humanities* is the leading subject. It is different from the international platforms where medical science is usually the most mentioned subject. These results suggest that WeChat mentions could be useful local altmetrics for China, have its unique characteristics and compliment the current altmetrics studies.

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